

Title: Weakly bound middle molecules in uremic plasma and variation with dialytic therapy

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Uremic plasma have been analyzed for free middle molecules (ultrafilterable) and weakly bound (WB) middle molecules (ultrafilterable after dilution) before and after haemodialysis or hemofiltration, by gel-chromatography and fluorimetric scan.

The results have showed:

- Free and WB middle molecules are present in large amounts in uremia.
- The ratio free/WB is variable from patient to patient.
- Both typer of treatment lower the amount of both free and wb middle molecules, which remain nevertheless at pathological levels.
- Peaks of fluorescent middle molecules resist to the excretory procedure.

Toxic molecules of single patients should be carefully evaluated (for molecular weight and protein binding) to execute a specific excretory technique (dialysis, filtration, anafiltration).